

New Therapeutic Agents of the Quinoline Series: Part I. Fused Quinolyl Compounds

B. Mohanty, P. C. Rath and M. K. Rout

By condensation of chroman-2, 4-diones, isocoumaranone, beta-tetralone, 5-methoxy 7-hydroxy indan-1, 3-dione with (1) anthranilic acid, (2) *o*-nitro benzaldehyde and (3) dimethoxy *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde followed by subsequent reduction of the *o*-nitrobenzylidene derivatives, heterocyclic compounds with fused quinoline rings were prepared and tested for their antispasmodic and antihistaminic properties.

Schonhofer¹ reported that the antispasmodic activity of quinoline is enhanced by introducing methoxy groups in quinoline rings. The thiazylquinoline and pyridylquinoline have also been reported² to be pharmacologically active as antispasmodics and anti-asthmatic. It was therefore considered of interest to investigate whether a similar enhancement of activity could be achieved in the heterocyclic compounds with fused quinoline rings by the introduction of one or more methoxy groups.

Condensation of chroman-2, 4-diones, isocoumaranone, beta-tetralone, 5-methoxy 7-hydroxy indan-1, 3-dione with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (or dimethoxy *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde) and subsequent reduction of these products have resulted in the formation of compounds having the structures I, II, III and IV ($R=H$ or OCH_3 and $X=H$ or OH) respectively as given below:

1. *Medicine in its chemical aspects*, 1934, II, 229; Coates *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 401.
2. Ellinger, Koschura and Secer, *Klin. Woch.*, 1934, 13, 411; F.P. 760, 823, Slotta and Haberland, *Angew. Chem.*, 1933, 46, 766.

Products obtained by the condensation of the ketones and ketolactones under discussion with anthranilic acid have the structures (I—IV; R=H or -OCH₃, and X=OH).

4,5-dimethoxy *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde³, chroman 2,4-diones (4-hydroxy coumarines)⁴, beta-tetralone⁵, 5-methoxy 7-hydroxy indan-1, 3-dione⁶ were obtained by the methods reported in literature.

Isocoumaranone was however obtained by the method of Chatterjee⁷ by the cyclisation of *o*-hydroxy phenyl acetic acid under vacuum.

The spasmolytic activities of these compounds against acetyl choline chloride and histamin acid phosphate spasms of isolated guinea-pig ileum were determined by Magnus method and the results revealed that most of these compounds are very potent spasmolytics and compare well with the activities of known antispasmodics and antihistaminics.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-(*o*-Nitrobenzylidene)-7-hydroxy chroman 2,4-dione: To 7-hydroxy chroman 2,4-dione (1.78 g) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1.50 g) in hot glacial acetic acid (30 cc), fused sodium acetate (1.50 g) was added and the mixture was refluxed for three hours. It was then cooled and added to an excess of water when a precipitate appeared. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight, after which the solids were filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol; m.p. >260°C, yield 65% (Found: C, 61.03; H, 2.84. C₁₉H₉O₆N requires C, 61.73; H, 2.80%)

The analytical data etc. of other related compounds of this series are given in the following table.

TABLE I

Name of the Compound	Nucleus	A	R	Yield%	M.P. °C	Analysis percentage			
						Carbon		Hydrogen	
						Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
3-(2'-Nitrobenzylidene)-5,6-benzochroman-2,4-dione	5,6-Benzochroman		H	45	155	68.15	69.56	3.15	3.19
3-(2'-Nitro-4', 5-di-methoxybenzylidene)-5,6-benzochroman-2,4-dione	do		-OCH ₃	51	176	65.06	65.18	3.61	3.70
3-(2'-Nitrobenzylidene)-7,8-benzochroman-2,4-dione	7,8-benzochroman		H	44	300	69.32	69.56	3.15	3.19

3. R. Robinson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1236.

4. V. R. Shah *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 677.

5. R. Robinson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 689.

6. R. Black *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 272.

7. Chatterjee, S. N.; University Professor of Chemistry, Science College, Patna; Personal communications.

TABLE I (contd.)

Name of the compound	Nucleus	A R	Yield%	M.P. °C	Analysis percentage			
					Carbon		Hydrogen	
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
3-(2'-Nitro-4', 5'-dimethoxy benzylidene)								
—7,8-benzochroman	do	-OCH ₃	48	260	64.85	65.18	3.59	3.70
—2,4-dione								
2-(2'-Nitrobenzylidene)								
—isocoumaranone	Isocoumaranone	H	71	112	65.95	67.42	3.34	3.37
2-(2'-Nitro-4', 5'-dimethoxy benzylidene)								
—isocoumaranone	do	-OCH ₃	44	260	61.83	62.38	3.94	3.98
2-(2'-Nitrobenzylidene)	5-Methoxy							
—5-methoxy, 7-hydroxy	7-hydroxy	H	74	220	61.89	62.76	3.29	3.39
—indan 1, 3-dione	indan -1,3-dione							
3-(2'-Nitro-4'5' dimethoxy benzylidene)	7-Hydroxy chroman	-OCH ₃	35	260	58.05	58.22	3.39	3.50
—7-hydroxychroman-2,4-dione	—2,4-dione							

7-Hydroxy 3,4-(3'2'-quinoly) Chroman-2-one: 3-(o-Nitrobenzylidene) 7-hydroxy-chroman—2,4-dione (1.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (30 cc) was refluxed in presence of zinc dust. Reflux was continued until it became nearly colourless which took about 4 hours. The exact duration was found out by testing for the absence of nitro group in the reaction mixture. After the reduction was complete, the resulting mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate was poured into a large volume of water when a brown precipitate gradually separated out. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and dilute hydrochloric acid followed by water and the desired product was obtained by extraction with and crystallisation from alcohol; m.p. 232°, yield 40% (found C, 71.35; H, 3.31. C₁₆H₉NO₃ requires C, 73.0; H, 3.42%)

Analytical data etc. of the related compounds of this series are given in table II.

TABLE II

Name of the compound	Yield%	M.P.	Analysis percentage			
			Carbon		Hydrogen	
		°C	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
3,4-(3'2'-Quinoly) —5,6-benzochroman	59	167	79.51	80.79	3.63	3.70
—2-one						
3,4-[3',2'-(6'7'-Dimethoxy) quinoly]	57	190	72.86	73.94	4.18	4.20
—5,6-benzochroman-2-one						
3,4-(3'2'-Quinoly)—7,8-benzochroman	60	178-80	80.15	80.79	3.63	3.70
—2-one						
3,4-[3'2'-(6'7'-Dimethoxy) quinoly]	69	185	72.89	73.94	4.15	4.20
—7,8-benzochroman—2-one						
2,3-(2'3'-Quinoly)-coumarone	68	108	81.05	82.21	4.07	4.11
2,3-[2'3'-(6'7'-Dimethoxy) quinoly]	53	230	72.09	73.11	4.59	4.66
—coumarone						
1,2-(3'2'-Quinoly) —3,4-dihydronaphthalene	65	105	87.15	88.31	5.58	5.63
1,2-[3'2'-(6'7'-Dimethoxy)quinoly]	47	190	77.85	78.34	5.78	5.84
—3,4-dihydronaphthalene						
7-Hydroxy-3,4-[3',2'-(6'7'-dimethoxy-quinoly)]-chroman-2-one	70	245	66.71	66.88	3.96	4.02
1-Hydroxy-6-methoxy-4-aza-2,3-benzofluoren-9-one	51	93-5	72.85	73.64	3.88	3.97

2,3-2',3' (4'-Hydroxy quinoly) coumarone: Iso-coumarone (1.3 g) and anthranilic acid (1.3 g) were fused at 150-60° and fused sodium acetate (1.3 g) was added during one hour period. The fused mass was then cooled, washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution to remove unreacted anthranilic acid. The residue was dissolved in alkali and reprecipitated by acid. The solid thus obtained was crystallized from alcohol; m.p. 93-5°, yield 58% (Found C, 75.95; H, 3.80. C₁₅H₉O₂N requires C, 76.60; H, 3.83%).

The analytical data etc. of the related compounds of this series are given in the table III.

TABLE III

Name of compound	Yield %	M.P. °C	Analysis percentage			
			Carbon		Hydrogen	
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
7-Hydroxy-3,4-[3',2'-(4'-hydroxy) quinoly]-chroman-2-one	62	237	67.85	68.82	9.19	9.23
3,4-[3',2'-(4-hydroxy) quinoly]-5,6-benzochroman-2-one	73	220	74.85	76.68	9.48	9.52
3,4-[3',2'-(4'-hydroxy) quinoly]-7,8-benzochroman-2-one	70	168-70	75.32	76.68	9.47	9.52
1,2-[3',2'-(4-hydroxy) quinoly]-3,4-dihydronaphthalene	83	328-30	81.86	82.58	5.22	5.26
1,8-Dihydroxy-6-methoxy-4-aza-2,3-benzofluorene-9-one	59	230	68.97	69.61	9.71	9.75

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MAYURBHANJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE, CUTTACK-3.

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